

FACTORS INFLUENCING INTERNET BANKING ADOPTION AMONG UNDERGRADUATES IN SRI LANKA

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Introduction

Background of the Study

Internet banking is a banking method that gives a chance for consumers to do a wide range of financial and non-financial transactions through the website of the relevant bank. As the direct delivery channel for the services, the banking industry uses internet driven banking services (Holloway & Beatty, 2008). Previous studies revealed that there is a higher rate of Internet based banking users in other countries around the world (Alalwan et al., 2018). However, when it comes to Sri Lanka there is a very low level of internet driven banking services usage (Suraweera et al., 2011).

Research Problem

There are lot of researches found around the world about the internet banking and internet banking adoption among undergraduates. Less number of researches are found in Sri Lanka about the titles related to internet banking. It is hard to find researches to study about factors that influence for undergraduates' adoption to internet banking in Sri Lanka. Undergraduates were used as the population because they are the ones who interact mostly with new technologies today. Hence, this study was done to identify the factors that influence internet banking adoption among undergraduates and to identify the relationship between the finding factors to fill that knowledge gap of smaller number of researches in Sri Lankan context related to this title.

Research Objectives

Identify the factors that affect internet banking adoption and find the relationship between the finding factors and internet banking.

Methodology

Approach to research:

The quantitative research approach has been used in this study.

Population and Sample:

Population was banking users in Sri Lanka. As the population was large, sample has been selected using convenience and random sampling techniques for this research. Sample size is identified base on 'ex ante power analysis' static calculator of 'danielsoper.com' and the sample size was 91. Therefore, sample will be limit to the undergraduates of University of Sri Jayewardenepura.

Approach to Data Collection:

Primary data was the type of data used in this study. Data has been collected by creating a questionnaire using google form and distributing it among the sample.

Measurements of Variable

Variables have been measured using SmartPLS and following instruments were used for this study.

- Only accept the item if outer loading value is greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2014). A threshold of 0.70 is used to validate the reliability of measurement scales (Hair et al., 2014)
- Convergent validity for each construct and a common rule of thumb is AVE is greater than 0.50 (Hair, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2011).
- The square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each construct should be much larger than the correlation of specific

construct with any other constructs in the conceptual model and should be at least 0.50 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the adapted framework for this study. This framework was adapted from the previous article. Factors determining banking customers attitudes towards the Internet Banking are recognized according to the Technology Acceptance Model and Theory of Reasoned Action and also previous studies. Those factors were Perceived Usefulness, Subjective Norms, Perceived Ease of Use, and Perceived Risk (Priyangika, Perera & Rajapakshe, 2017).

Intention to use Internet Banking constructor was removed from the model because it is not relevant to answer the research questions in the study. Therefore, following model has been used for this study.

Figure 1. Adapted Conceptual Framework

Results and Discussion

Testing the Research Model

According to outer loading values of this model, there was one item that value is less than 0.7. Therefore that item showed the weak relationship with the value of 0.692. According to Hair et al. (2014), a common rule of thumb is accepting the item if outer loading value is greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2014). Hence, this one item was eliminated from this model. After eliminating this item PLS algorithm was run to get a better model. Then all the outer loadings values were above 0.7 and this represents that all questionnaire items had strong relationship with their constructs.

Indicator Reliability

All items are reliable after removing that item which had 0.692 outer loading value.

Internal Consistency

All values under Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability were greater than 0.70 as suggested by Hair et al. (2014) and thus internal consistency was established.

Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is confirmed in all constructs as all the AVE values were above the 0.50. Hence convergent validity of this given research model is confirmed.

Discriminant Validity

Since none of the constructs' cross-correlations (off-diagonal elements) exceeded the respective square root of each construct's AVE (diagonal elements). Thus discriminant validity was established in the study.

R-Square

Hence it can be concluded that the predictability of independent variables towards dependent variability is 0.357 (35.7%).

Hypotheses Testing and Discussion

Four hypotheses were tested to find out the factors Influencing Internet Banking Adoption Among Undergraduates in Sri Lanka.

Table 1. Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses	Path Coefficient	Path	T-statistics	P value	Decision
H1	Perceived Ease of Use → Attitude Towards Internet Banking	0.200	1.484	0.139	Rejected
H2	Perceived Usefulness → Attitude Towards Internet Banking	0.301	2.049	0.041	Accepted
H3	Perceived Risk → Attitude Towards Internet Banking	0.018	0.005	0.996	Rejected
H4	Subjective Norms → Attitude Towards Internet Banking	0.199	1.771	0.077	Rejected

H1 : Perceived Ease of Use influences positively on Attitude Towards Internet Banking

There were not enough evidence to say that Perceived Ease of Use influences positively on Attitude Towards Internet Banking with p value 0.139. This means that Perceived Ease Of Use does not positively influence on Attitude Towards Internet Banking. Hence this hypothesis was Rejected.

H2 : Perceived Usefulness influences positively on Attitude Towards Internet Banking.

It proved that Perceived Usefulness influences positively on Attitude Towards Internet Banking with p value 0.041. This means that Perceived Usefulness positively influences on Attitude Towards Internet Banking. Hence this hypothesis was Accepted.

H3 : Perceived Risk influences negatively on Attitude Towards Internet Banking.

There were not enough evidence to say that Perceived Risk influences negatively on Attitude Towards Internet Banking with p value 0.996. This means that Perceived Risk does not negatively influence on Attitude Towards Internet Banking. Hence this hypothesis was Rejected.

H4 : Subjective Norms influences positively on Attitude Towards Internet Banking.

There were not enough evidence to say that Subjective Norms influences positively on Attitude Towards Internet Banking with p value 0.077. This means that Subjective Norms do not positively influence on Attitude Towards Internet Banking. Hence this hypothesis was Rejected.

Conclusion

Summary of findings

This study was done to investigate about the factors influencing internet banking adoption among undergraduates in Sri Lanka. Hence, Attitude Towards Internet Banking, Perceived Ease OF Use, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Risk and Subjective Norms were analyzed. The reliability and validity were confirmed through that.

In the hypothesis testing four hypotheses were tested and following results were obtained.

- Perceived Ease Of Use does not positively influence on Attitude Towards Internet Banking (Rejected)
- Perceived Usefulness positively influences on Attitude Towards Internet Banking (Accepted)
- Perceived Risk does not negatively influence on Attitude Towards Internet Banking (Rejected)
- Subjective Norms do not positively influence on Attitude Towards Internet Banking (Rejected)

According to those results one hypothesis was accepted and other three hypotheses were rejected.

Implications

There was no proper research to identify the factors influencing internet banking adoption among undergraduates in Sri Lanka. Main target of this study was to fill that knowledge gap.

Banks too can get ideas about the affecting factors for the internet banking. Hence, they can make their decisions relating to internet banking, using the findings of this study as they want.

There are many people who are still using traditional methods for banking because of lack of computer literacy. Hence, relevant administration parties should be involved to increase computer literacy and then the internet banking usage will be increased.

Limitations of the Study

The data was collected from only one university in Sri Lanka. However, there are 15 universities which are registered under the University Grants Commission in Sri Lanka. Hence, it is important to understand the situation of other universities as well.

Limited number of respondents also was a limiting factor for the study. If the sample size is large, the accuracy of data also increases.

The online survey technique was suitable for collecting information only from the people who have internet facilities. It is also limitation for this study.

Recommendations for Future Researches

This study showed the factors that affect for adoption of internet banking among young generation and the relationship between that identified factors among young generation. Hence, there is a gap to fill what factors affect for the Internet Banking adoption among other ages like middle age people and also elder ages. Further future researchers can use this study as a guideline and also, they can use the theories which are used in this study for them and fill those gaps. Furthermore, they can continue their studies by avoiding above limitations too.

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